

RESISTANCE OF MATERIALS AND THEIR USE IN INDUSTRY

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Abstract - The resistance of materials is a science that studies the strength and deformability of construction elements and machine parts, their susceptibility to processing, the physical-mechanical properties of materials used in their preparation, and the characteristics specific to their structure. The main task is to develop methods of calculating static and dynamic forces on elements and details, strength, uniform stiffness, stability and vibrations.

Key words: theoretical mechanics, applied mechanics, dynamics, statics, materials, specific resistance, specific gravity, iron, zinc, copper, machine tools, machines.

The main objects of study are rods and plates, which are studied in theoretical and practical methods. Elements and details are made of rods and plates. Material selection is a crucial part of any manufacturing process. Choosing the right material is so important because the material defines the chemical and mechanical properties of the component being manufactured, can significantly influence the longevity of the component, and ensures that part functions properly. Corrosion-resistant materials play a significant role in manufacturing because of their material properties and their lack of reactivity to harsh environmental conditions and chemicals. For example, many aerospace components are manufactured using titanium, tungsten, and carbon fiber because these materials are very strong, yet lightweight and flexible. Unfortunately, these materials can react with one another and cause galvanic corrosion over time, localized corrosion where there's an exchange of ions between materials. Here, corrosion-resistant materials preserve the integrity of parts in one of the most strictly regulated industries in the world.

The theoretical part of the resistance of materials is based on the laws of theoretical mechanics, the change of shape, crushing and the theory of elastic deformation of bodies. The practical part is based on various tests, principles of physics and material science. The methods, norms and recommendations developed by the science of resistance of materials are used in engineering practice to determine the greatest stresses and displacements in elements and details and to compare them with normative values and standards that are safe for the use of structures and machines. Special testing machines and measuring devices are used in experimental studies. According to the research results, target "stress-deformation" diagrams are drawn up, strength, yield limits and elasticity indicators of the material are determined. These allow to determine the most stressed areas, deformable and displacement areas of the calculated element or detail. During the design or inspection, the dimensions and shape of the element or detail are determined by comparing the calculated values of stresses and deformations with the values allowed in the standards with the help of target diagrams. The theoretical conclusions and practical results of the science of resistance of materials are very important in ensuring the priority and earthquake resistance of buildings, extending the service life of machines and mechanisms, increasing the durability and quality of clothing,

especially in aviation and cosmonautic. The main goal is to create practical, simple methods for calculating the most common structural elements. The need to bring the solution of every practical problem to a numerical result requires the use of approximate methods. The simplicity of the conclusions in some cases, however, leads to hypotheses close to the truth. Their legitimacy is based, on the one hand, on the consistency of the obtained results, and on the other hand, by the conclusions drawn on the fine analysis of the theory of elasticity. The resistance of materials and the theory of elasticity interact. Most of what is created by the theory of elasticity is accepted by the resistance course of materials and organically corresponds to their composition. At the same time, due to its practical orientation, the resistance of materials solves a wider range of problems than the mathematical theory of elasticity. There are many issues. But the main thing is that the resistance of materials leads the reader to inevitable and eternal questions, which are sometimes difficult to answer, does the structure stand or not, is it strong or not, and what is its reliability. In the theory of elasticity, such questions are 'liq. Is not taken into account.

Summary. The theoretical conclusions and practical results of the science of resistance of materials are very important in ensuring the priority and earthquake resistance of buildings, in extending the service life of machines and mechanisms, in increasing the durability and quality of clothes, especially in aviation and cosmonautics. Steel is among the metal building materials. the most common, and the durability is considered high.

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